

The spectrum of $P_{(k,10-k)}^{(5)}$ -designs

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Abstract

Given an hypergraph $H^{(h)}$, uniform of rank h , an $H^{(h)}$ -design [or also a design of type $H^{(h)}$] of order v is a pair $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$, where X is a set of cardinality v and $\mathcal{B}$ is a collection of hypergraphs, all isomorphic to $H^{(h)}$, such that every h -subset of X is an edge of exactly one hypergraph $H^{(h)} \in \mathcal{B}$. An hyperpath $P_2^{(h)}$ is an uniform hypergraph, having two non disjoint edges. In this paper we determine the spectrum of hyperpath-designs of type $P_2^{(5)}$, in the case that hyperedges have 3 or 4 vertices in common and formulate a conjecture about the cases $k = 1, 2$.

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1 Introduction

Let $K_v^{(h)} = (X, \mathcal{E})$ be the complete hypergraph, uniform of rank h , defined in the vertex set $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_v\}$, for $v \geq h$. This means that $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{P}_h(X)$, the collection of all the h -subsets of X .

Let $H^{(h)}$ be a subhypergraph of $K_v^{(h)}$. An $H^{(h)}$ -design [or also a design of type $H^{(h)}$], having order v , is a pair $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$, where X is a finite set of cardinality v , whose elements are called *vertices*, and $\mathcal{B}$ is a collection of hypergraphs, also called *blocks*, all isomorphic to $H^{(h)}$, with the condition that every h -subset Y of X is an edge of exactly one hypergraph $H^{(h)} \in \mathcal{B}$. An $H^{(h)}$ -design, of order v , is also called an $H^{(h)}$ -decomposition of $K_v^{(h)}$ [1].

In what follows, we will indicate by $Sp(H^{(h)})$ the *spectrum* of the correspondent $H^{(h)}$ -designs, i.e. the set of all integers v such that there exist $H^{(h)}$ -designs of order v .

Observe that:

- Among all the graphs, there is exactly one path with two edges and it is known as P_3 . If x, y, z are the vertices of a path P_3 and the edges are $\{x, y\}, \{y, z\}$, we will indicate it by $[x, (y), z]$.
- Among all the uniform hypergraphs of rank 3, there are exactly two *hyperpaths* with two edges. The number of vertices can be 4 or 5. A $P^{(3)}(2, 4)$ will be the hyperpath having vertices a, b, c, d and edges $\{a, b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}$, and it will be indicate by $[a, (b, c), d]$. A $P^{(3)}(1, 5)$ will be the hyperpath having vertices a, b, c, d, e and edges $\{a, b, c\}, \{c, d, e\}$, and it will be indicated by $[a, b, (c), d, e]$.
- Among all the hypergraphs uniform of rank 4, there are exactly three *hyperpaths* with two edges. The number of vertices can be 5 or 6 or 7. A $P^{(4)}(3, 5)$ will be the hyperpath having vertices a, b, c, d, e and edges $\{a, b, c, d\}, \{b, c, d, e\}$, and it will be indicate by $[a, (b, c, d), e]$. A $P^{(4)}(2, 6)$ will be the hyperpath having vertices a, b, c, d, e, f and edges $\{a, b, c, d\}, \{c, d, e, f\}$, and it will be indicate by $[a, b, (c, d), e, f]$. A $P^{(4)}(1, 7)$ will be the hyperpath having vertices a, b, c, d, e, f, g and edges $\{a, b, c, d\}, \{d, e, f, g\}$, and it will be indicate by $[a, b, c, (d), e, f, g]$.

For $h = 2$, $H^{(2)}$ is a graph G and G -designs have been studied in the recent past by many authors.

For $h = 3$, $H^{(3)}$ -designs have been studied in [2], where the spectrum has been determined in some cases of hypergraphs $H^{(3)}$ with few edges. *Balanced* $H^{(3)}$ -designs have been studied in [4]. Other general results can be found in [1].

For $h = 4$, $H^{(4)}$ -designs have been studied in [3], where the spectrum has been determined for $P^{(4)}(3, 5)$ -designs, $P^{(4)}(2, 6)$ -designs and $P^{(4)}(1, 7)$ -designs, where $P^{(4)}(u, 8 - u)$, for $u = 1, 2, 3$, is an hyperpath with two edges, i.e. an uniform hypergraph of rank 4, of order $8 - u$, with two edges having u vertices in common.

It is known that:

Theorem 1.1 : $Sp(P_3) = \{v \in N : v \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ mod } 4, v \geq 4\}$.

Theorem 1.2 : $Sp(P^{(3)}(6 - u, u)) = \{v \in N : v \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 2 \text{ mod } 4, v \geq u, \text{ for } u = 4, 5\}$. [2]

Some proof of the previous theorems can be found in [2] and also in [1]. For $P^{(4)}(3, 5)$, $P^{(4)}(2, 6)$, $P^{(4)}(1, 7)$, in [3] it is proved that:

Theorem 1.3 : $Sp(P^{(4)}(3, 5)) = Sp(P^{(4)}(2, 6)) = Sp(P^{(4)}(1, 7)) = \{v \in N : v \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 2 \text{ or } 3 \text{ mod } 8, v \geq 8\}$. [3]

In this paper we study the spectrum for $P^{(5)}(4, 6)$ -designs $P^{(5)}(3, 7)$ -designs and determine it completely. Further, we formulate a conjecture regarding

The spectrum of $P_{(k,10-k)}^{(5)}$ -designs

$P^{(5)}(2, 8)$ -designs and $P^{(5)}(1, 9)$ -designs. The motivation for this research is to study the trend of the spectrum of $P^{(h)}(k, 2h - k)$ -designs. We will see that for $h = 5$ the situation is similar to the case $h = 3$, while in the cases $h = 2, h = 4$ the trend is the same.

In what follows, for a given $P_{(k,2h-k)}^{(h)}$ -design $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$, if $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p\} \subseteq X$ and $\{x, y, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{h-p-1}\} \subseteq X$, then $[x, (A, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{h-p-1}), y]$ will indicate the block of Σ having for h -edges $\{x, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{h-p-1}\}$ and $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{h-p-1}, y\}$.

2 General results

In [3] the authors proved the following general results.

Theorem 2.1 : If $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_2^{(h)}$ -design of order v , for any h , then:

- 1) $|\mathcal{B}| = \binom{v}{h}/2$;
- 2) if $P_2^{(h)} = P^{(h)}(k, 2h - k)$, then $v \geq 2h - k$.

Theorem 2.2 - If Σ is a $P_2^{(h)}(k, 2h - k)$ -design of order v , Γ a $P_2^{(h-1)}(k - 1, 2h - k - 1)$ -design of the same order v , then there exists a $P_2^{(h)}(k, 2h - k)$ -design Σ' of order $v' = v + 1$, embedding Σ .

3 Necessary conditions for $P_2^{(5)}$ -designs

We have that:

Theorem 3.1 : If $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_2^{(5)}(k, 10 - k)$ -design of order v , then v is even or $v \equiv 1$ or $3 \pmod{8}$, with always $v \geq 10 - k$.

Proof. For $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$, if $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_2^{(5)}$ -design of order v , then:

$$|\mathcal{B}| = \binom{v}{5}/2 = \frac{v(v-1)(v-2)(v-3)(v-4)}{5 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 1} \cdot \frac{1}{2}.$$

From which, necessarily, it follows that or v is even or $v = 8k + 1$ or $v = 8k + 3$. Further, if $B \in \mathcal{B}$ and the two edges of B have k vertices in common for $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$, then $|B| = 10 - k$ and therefore $v \geq 10 - k$. $\square$

4 The spectrum of $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -designs

In this section we determine all the positive integer v such that there exist $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -designs of order v .

Theorem 4.1 - *There exist $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -designs of order $v = 6$.*

Proof. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_8\}$. Consider the family $\mathcal{B}$ of the following hypergraphs:

$$\begin{aligned} & [x_1, (X - \{x_1, x_2\}), x_2], \\ & [x_3, (X - \{x_3, x_4\}), x_4], \\ & [x_5, (X - \{x_5, x_6\}), x_6]. \end{aligned}$$

It is immediate to verify that $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v = 6$. $\square$

Theorem 4.2 - *If $v \in Sp(P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}) \cap Sp(P_{(3,5)}^{(4)})$, then $v + 1 \in Sp(P_{(4,6)}^{(5)})$.*

Proof. *Construction $v \rightarrow v + 1$.*

Let $\Sigma_1 = (X, \mathcal{B}_1)$ be a $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -design and let $\Sigma_2 = (X, \mathcal{B}_2)$ be a $P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}$ -design, both of order v . Let $\infty \notin X$, $X' = X \cup \{\infty\}$. Define the following family Π of hypergraphs $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$:

$$\Pi = \{[x', (\infty, x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}), x''] : [x', (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}), x''] \in \mathcal{B}_2\}.$$

If $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}_1 \cup \Pi$, then $\Sigma = (X', \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v + 1$.

Indeed, consider any $Y \subseteq X'$, $|Y| = 5$. If $Y \subseteq X$, there exists exactly one block $B \in \mathcal{B}_1$ having Y as edge and also no block of Π has Y as edge. If $\infty \in Y$ and therefore $|Y \cap X| = 4$, then there exists exactly one block of $B \in \mathcal{B}_2$ containing $Y - \{\infty\}$ as edge in Σ_2 and therefore there exists exactly one block of Π containing Y as edge.

The statement is so proved. $\square$

Theorem 4.3 - *If $v \in Sp(P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}) \cap Sp(P_{(2,4)}^{(3)})$, v even, then $v + 2 \in Sp(P_{(4,6)}^{(5)})$.*

Proof. *Construction $v \rightarrow v + 2$.*

Let $\infty_1, \infty_2 \notin X$, $\infty_1 \neq \infty_2$, $X' = X \cup \{\infty_1, \infty_2\}$. Further, let

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_1 &= (X, \mathcal{B}_1) \text{ be a } P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}\text{-design of order } v; \\ \Sigma_2 &= (X, \mathcal{B}_2) \text{ be a } P_{(2,4)}^{(3)}\text{-design of order } v. \end{aligned}$$

The spectrum of $P_{(k,10-k)}^{(5)}$ -designs

Define the following families of hypergraphs $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$:

$$\Pi_1 = \{[x', (\infty_1, \infty_2, x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x'') : [x', (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x'')] \in \mathcal{B}_2\};$$

$$\Pi_2 = \{[\infty_1, (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}, x_{j,4}), \infty_2] : \{x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}, x_{j,4}\} \in \mathcal{P}_4(X)\}.$$

If $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}_1 \cup \Pi_1, \Pi_2$, it is possible to verify that $\Sigma = (X', \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v + 2$, which proves the statement. $\square$

Collecting together the results proved in the previous Theorems, it follows that:

Theorem 4.4 - *There exist $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -designs if and only if:*

1) v is even, $v \geq 6$;

or

2) $v \equiv 1$ or $v \equiv 3, \text{ mod } 8$.

Proof. The statement follows from Theorems 4.1, 4.3, considering that for $v \geq 8$, v even, $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -designs of order v there exist. The statement 2) follows from 1) and Theorem 4.2, considering that for $v = 8h$ and $v = 8h + 2$, for any $h \in \mathbb{N}$, $P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}$ -designs of order v there exist. $\square$

5 An extension to $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -designs

By the same technique used for $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -designs it is possible to determine the spectrum of $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -designs.

Theorem 5.1 - *There exist $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -designs of order $v = 8$.*

Proof. Let $X = \{1, 2, \dots, 8\}$. Consider the family $\mathcal{B}$ of the following hypergraphs:

$$\begin{aligned} & [4, 5, (1, 2, 3), 6, 8], [3, 7, (1, 2, 5), 4, 6], [3, 4, (1, 2, 7), 6, 8], [2, 6, (1, 3, 4), 5, 8], \\ & [2, 8, (1, 3, 5), 4, 6], [2, 7, (1, 4, 5), 6, 8], [2, 8, (1, 4, 7), 3, 5], [3, 7, (1, 2, 6), 4, 8], \\ & [2, 3, (1, 7, 8), 4, 6], [1, 8, (2, 3, 4), 5, 6], [2, 3, (6, 7, 8), 4, 5], [1, 2, (5, 6, 8), 3, 7], \\ & [1, 6, (2, 3, 5), 7, 8], [3, 8, (2, 4, 6), 5, 7], [1, 6, (2, 4, 7), 5, 8], [3, 7, (2, 5, 6), 4, 8], \\ & [1, 3, (6, 7, 8), 2, 5], [1, 5, (2, 7, 8), 3, 4], [1, 8, (3, 4, 6), 5, 7], [1, 7, (3, 4, 6), 5, 8], \\ & [1, 8, (3, 4, 7), 2, 6], [1, 5, (3, 6, 8), 4, 7], [1, 6, (4, 5, 7), 3, 8], [1, 7, (4, 5, 8), 2, 3], \\ & [1, 5, (6, 7, 8), 2, 4], [1, 6, (3, 5, 7), 2, 4], [2, 6, (1, 5, 7), 3, 8], [1, 4, (2, 5, 8), 3, 6]. \end{aligned}$$

It is immediate to verify that $\Sigma = (X, \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(4,6)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v = 8$.

Theorem 5.2 - If $v \in Sp(P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}) \cap Sp(P_{(2,6)}^{(4)})$, then $v + 1 \in Sp(P_{(3,7)}^{(5)})$.

Proof. Construction $v \rightarrow v + 1$.

Let $\Sigma_1 = (X, \mathcal{B}_1)$ be a $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -design and let $\Sigma_2 = (X, \mathcal{B}_2)$ be a $P_{(2,6)}^{(4)}$ -design, both of order v . Let $\infty \notin X$, $X' = X \cup \{\infty\}$. Define the following family Π of hypergraphs $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$:

$$\Pi = \{[x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, (\infty, x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}), x_{3,i}, x_{4,i}] : [x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}), x_{3,i}, x_{4,i}] \in \mathcal{B}_2\}.$$

If $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}_1 \cup \Pi$, it is possible to verify that $\Sigma = (X', \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v + 1$, which proves the statement. $\square$

Theorem 5.3 - If $v \in Sp(P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}) \cap Sp(P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}) \cap Sp(P_{(1,5)}^{(3)})$, v even, then $v + 2 \in Sp(P_{(3,7)}^{(5)})$.

Proof. Construction $v \rightarrow v + 2$. Let $\infty_1, \infty_2 \notin X$, $\infty_1 \neq \infty_2$, $X' = X \cup \{\infty_1, \infty_2\}$. Further, let

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_1 &= (X, \mathcal{B}_1) \text{ be a } P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}\text{-design of order } v; \\ \Sigma_2 &= (X, \mathcal{B}_2) \text{ be a } P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}\text{-design of order } v; \\ \Sigma_3 &= (X, \mathcal{B}_3) \text{ be a } P_{(1,5)}^{(3)}\text{-design of order } v. \end{aligned}$$

Define the following families of hypergraphs $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_1 &= \{[[x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, (\infty_1, \infty_2, x_{j,1}), x_{i,3}, x_{i,4}] : [x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, (x_{j,1}), x_{3,i}, x_{4,i}] \in \mathcal{B}_3\}; \\ \Pi_2 &= \{[\infty_1, x_{i,1}, (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}), x_{i,2}, \infty_2] : [x_{i,1}, (x_{j,1}, x_{j,2}, x_{j,3}), x_{i,2}] \in \mathcal{B}_2\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}_1 \cup \Pi_1, \Pi_2$, it is possible to verify that $\Sigma = (X', \mathcal{B})$ is a $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -design of order $v + 2$, which proves the statement. $\square$

Collecting together the previous Theorems, it follows that:

Theorem 5.4 - There exist $P_{(3,7)}^{(5)}$ -designs if and only if:

1) v is even, $v \geq 8$;

or

2) $v \equiv 1$ or $v \equiv 3, \text{ mod } 8$.

Proof. The statement 1) follows from Theorems 5.1, 5.3, considering that $P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}$ -designs of order v exist for every v even, $v \geq 6$. The statement 2) follows from Theorems 5.1, 5.2, considering that $P_{(3,5)}^{(4)}$ -designs and $P_{(1,5)}^{(3)}$ -designs of order v exist for any $h \in \mathbb{N}$ and $v = 8h, v = 8h + 2$. $\square$

The spectrum of $P_{(k,10-k)}^{(5)}$ -designs

6 Conjecture for $k = 1$ and $k = 2$

It seems very difficult to determine the spectrum of $P_{(k,10-k)}^{(5)}$ -designs for $k = 1, 2$, i.e. for $P_{(1,9)}^{(5)}$ -designs and $P_{(2,8)}^{(5)}$ -designs. It is opinion of the authors that in these cases the spectrum is similar to the one already found for $k = 4$ and $k = 3$.

Conjecture: For $k = 1, 2$, there exist $P^{(5)}(k, 10 - k)$ -designs of order v if and only if: $v \geq 10 - k$ and
 $v \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ or $v \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$.

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